

Policy BRIEFs : List of Contributors – 2023

Policy brief N0	Policy Brief Title	Contributor(s)
1	REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation “GDPR”)	Chiara D’Elia Stefano Tramacere
2	The Principle of Accountability	Irina Carnat
3	The Right to Data Portability	Tommaso Crepax
4	Secondary Use of Health Data	Chiara D’Elia Stefano Tramacere
5	REGULATION (EU) NO 536/2014 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL OF 16 APRIL 2014 ON CLINICAL TRIALS ON MEDICINAL PRODUCTS FOR HUMAN USE, AND REPEALING DIRECTIVE 2001/20/EC CLINICAL TRIALS REGULATION (CTR)	Chiara D’Elia Stefano Tramacere
6	REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No	Chiara D’Elia Stefano Tramacere

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	<p>1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC</p> <p>MEDICAL DEVICES REGULATION (MDR)</p>	
7	<p>ITALIAN IMPLEMENTATIONS OF MDR AND CTR</p> <p>LEGISLATIVE DECREE 137/2022</p> <p>ITALIAN MINISTRY OF HEALTH</p> <p>DECREES OF 20.3.2023</p>	<p>Francesca Gennari Chiara D'Elia Stefano Tramacere</p>
8	<p>ITALIAN IMPLEMENTATIONS OF MDR AND CTR</p> <p>ITALIAN MINISTRY OF HEALTH</p> <p>DECREES OF 12.04.2023</p>	<p>Chiara D'Elia, Stefano Tramacere</p>